

POST-BUCKLING RESPONSE OF ISOTROPIC
AND LAMINATED COMPOSITE SQUARE PLATES WITH
CIRCULAR HOLES

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Abstract

In this paper the authors emphasize the well known anomalous behavior in buckling of square plates with centrally located cut-outs. For certain size holes and depending upon whether the loading is displacement or stress controlled, perforated square plates have higher buckling loads than equivalent solid plates. Because of this anomaly the authors have examined the post-buckling response of such plates of both isotropic and laminated composite construction. Having concluded from their post-buckling response that such plates are imperfection insensitive except for a slight loss of their post-buckling strength because of the presence of the hole, the authors go on to examine the possible weight savings in using perforated square plates to resist buckling.

Introduction

Buckling of perforated plates has been an area of interest to the technical community for many years. This interest stems from the fact that such plates are used extensively for a variety of holes-conduit holes and fastener holes in aircraft structures. Increasing demands for structural efficiency has brought about the use of advanced structural materials such as fiber reinforced laminated composites for such aircraft structures. Unfortunately, along with the improved structural performance provided by composites has also come a level of complexity much greater than that encountered in more conventional isotropic materials such as steel, aluminum and titanium. The buckling behavior of composite plates containing centrally located cut-outs is thus important to the technical community in that some very basic information essential to the design of sophisticated structural systems can be obtained from an in-depth study of such a behavior.

Buckling behavior of square plates with centrally located circular cut-outs is greatly influenced by the type of loading - stress or displacement controlled. Analyses and experiments indicate that the buckling resistance of isotropic square plates containing large centrally located circular holes increases with increasing hole size [1-4], see Figs. 1 and 2. Similar behavior is also observed in the case of 60° angle-ply laminates with central circular holes [4], see Fig. 3. Although, this anomalous behavior

Figure 1. Comparison of the finite element analysis with the experimental results for square isotropic simply-supported plates loaded by uniform axial compression.

Figure 2 Comparison of the finite element analysis with the experimental results for square isotropic simply-supported plates loaded by uniform axial displacement.

Figure 3. Buckling predictions for square simply-supported angle-ply laminates with circular holes loaded by uniform axial compression.

has been explained on the basis of radically different prebuckling stress distributions, it calls for a study of their post-buckling behavior with a view to determining their imperfection sensitivity. It also calls for an investigation of possible material savings realizable through proper use of perforated plates of laminated composite construction in buckling.

In this study, the post-buckling analysis of plates is carried out using the finite element displacement method. The plate is modelled with 16 noded, three dimensional isoparametric elements and the response of the resulting nonlinear finite element displacement model with an assumed sinusoidal imperfection is predicted using a globally convergent quasi-Newton method [5] incrementally.

Formulation and Solution of Problem

In the present study, the incremental Updated Lagrangian formulation [5,6] forms the basis for obtaining the post-buckling response of plates. This formulation expresses equilibrium at a particular load level in terms of the last known equilibrium configuration. The formulation can be stated using the principle of virtual displacements as

$$\int_{V_1} \Delta S_{ij} \delta \Delta E_{ij} dV_1 + \int_{V_1} {}^1\sigma_{ij} \delta \Delta \eta_{ij} dV_1 - \int_{A_1} \Delta T_i \delta \Delta u_i dA_1 = 0 \quad (1)$$

where

ΔS_{ij} = components of the incremental second Piola-Kirchoff stress tensor

ΔE_{ij} = components of the incremental Green Lagrangian strain tensor

${}^1\sigma_{ij}$ = components of the Cauchy stress tensor in the last known equilibrium configuration

$\Delta \eta_{ij}$ = components of the nonlinear part of the incremental Green Lagrangian strain tensor

ΔT_i = components of the incremental surface traction vector

Δu_i = components of the incremental displacement vector

V_1 = volume of body in last equilibrium configuration

A_1 = area of body in last equilibrium configuration

Equations (1) give rise to a system of nonlinear partial differential equations. By using the finite element modelling scheme for spatial discretization, a system of nonlinear algebraic equations result which have to be solved in order to obtain an approximate solution to the incremental problem.

An alternative is to approach the problem as one of unconstrained minimization that is, assuming the material to be linearly elastic and the loading to be incrementally conservative. An incremental potential energy function can then be constructed such that its gradient is equal to the discretized form of the left hand side of Eqs. (1). Such an incremental potential energy function can be easily verified to be given by

$$\Delta\pi = \frac{1}{2} \int_{V_1} \Delta S_{ij} \Delta E_{ij} dV_1 + \int_{V_1} \sigma_{ij} \Delta \eta_{ij} dV_1 - \int_{A_1} \Delta T_i \Delta u_i dA_1 \quad (2)$$

Using as before, the finite element modelling scheme for spatial discretization, the incremental potential energy function can be expressed as a nonlinear function of unknown displacement increments. Minimization of this function then yields the solution to the incremental problem. The algorithm used to minimize the nonlinear, incremental potential energy function is a modified Newton-Raphson method that is rendered globally convergent through the use of a Model Trust region approach described in detail in reference [5] and [7].

The buckling load was calculated, from the post-buckling response curve, as the load which corresponds to its horizontal asymptote signifying the initiation of large out of plane displacements. This calculation may be in error by about one or two percent from the exact buckling load. So that buckling load was occasionally verified by locating the load level on the response curve at which the exact Hessian of the total potential energy ceases to be positive definite. During the course of the nonlinear analysis using the incremental Updated Lagrangian formulation, in the vicinity of the buckling load, the loss of positive definiteness of the Hessian matrix of the incremental potential function of Eq. (2) was at times encountered. The globally convergent modified Newton-Raphson method of reference [5] however eliminates all problems associated with such a loss of positive definiteness of the Hessian matrix by using Gill-Murray's strategy [5] to coerce the Hessian into a positive definite matrix if needed.

Isotropic Plates with Circular Holes

In this study, the plate is modelled with sixteen noded, three dimensional isoparametric elements using two elements through the thickness in the case of isotropic plates (see Figs. 4 and 5). Even though Figs. 4 and 5 show the discretization for half the plate only a quarter plate was modelled for all fiber orientations since it was known a priori that the lowest buckling mode was symmetric about both the x and y axes. The points A, B, C, and D in Fig. 4 are points which correspond to edges of holes of different sizes. The displacements at these points in the solid plate are used when comparing the post-buckling response of plates with holes. The response of the nonlinear finite element displacement model of a typical quarter plate with or without a hole with an assumed imperfection is predicted using the algorithm alluded to earlier. The initial imperfection was assumed to be

$$z_0/H_0 = 0.001 \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2W}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi y}{W}\right) \quad (3)$$

Results of the response predictions are shown in Figs. 6 through 9. These studies reveal that isotropic square plates with large holes ($d/W = 0.6$, $d =$ diameter of the hole and $W =$ width of the plate) lose some of their post-buckling strength but they are not imperfection sensitive. That is, perforated plates continue to carry substantial additional compressive load in the post-buckling range. As a matter of fact, with stress controlled loading, the amount of material in a perforated plate with $d/W = 0.6$ is nearly 20% less than that in a solid plate with the same buckling load (see Fig. 10).

Angle Ply Laminated Composite Plates with Circular Holes

Angle ply laminated composite plates with circular holes were analyzed using the same three dimensional isoparametric elements, however, four elements were used through the thickness instead of two in the case of isotropic plates. The same imperfection, Eq. (3), was assumed. The specific type of laminated composite plates that were analyzed were $[\theta, -\theta]$. The fiber orientations θ , considered were 0° , 30° , 45° , 60° and for the loading was used since this kind of loading yields the least increase of buckling load by comparison with displacement loading for perforated plates. The solid plate was first analyzed for these four cases with $n = 5$, then plates with holes were analyzed with different values of n so as to get approximately the same buckling load. Typical responses for plates with $\theta = 60^\circ$ can be found in Figs. 11-12. For sake of convenience, all the results for the different fiber orientations are tabulated in Table 1. In all these cases a single three dimensional isoparametric element was used through n layers leading to a total of four elements through the thickness of the plate.

The first observation from these figures is that these composite plates are not imperfection sensitive. That is to say, they are able to carry substantial additional load in the post-buckling range. For sake of convenience, all the results for the different fiber orientations are tabulated in Table 1. The results of Table 1 agree with the results of Fig. 3. That is, for the 0° and 30° angle ply laminates, the buckling load decreases continuously as the hole size increases. For the 45° angle ply laminate the buckling load levels off for large holes and for the 60° angle ply laminate the buckling load of plates with large holes actually begins to increase above that of the corresponding solid plate.

As alluded to in the introduction, the purpose of this study was to determine whether or not some material savings could be realized by using a plate with a hole to resist buckling. From Table 1, one can see a comparison of volumes for the same buckling load. The value of n was changed in order to obtain a buckling load approximately equal to that of the plate with no hole. It is clear that for large holes there is a material savings in each case except the 0° laminate. This material savings however is compensated for by a slight loss of the post-buckling strength as is evident from Figs. 11-12 for the plates with 60° orientation. However, like isotropic plates, perforated, laminated composite plates do continue to carry load beyond the buckling load and are definitely not imperfection sensitive in spite of the presence of the hole.

Conclusions

It has been shown that for both isotropic square plates and angle ply laminated composite square plates with circular cut-outs, a material savings can be realized when such plates are used to resist buckling. However, there is some loss of their post-buckling strength even though the plates continue to carry additional load in the post-buckling range just like the solid plates. This is to say that plates with large holes are not imperfection sensitive. It was also determined that in the case of the 60° angle ply laminate, the buckling load actually increases above that of the corresponding solid plate of the same fiber orientation as the hole gets large ($d/W \geq 0.6$) so that there appears to be a bigger pay off in terms of material saving for this case.

TABLE 1

Weight Requirements of Perforated, Square, Laminated Composite Plates

$$[\theta_n, -\theta_n]_s$$

Fiber Orientation θ	Number of Layers n	$d/W = 0.0$		$d/W = 0.05$		$d/W = 0.2$		$d/W = 0.6$	
		Normalized Buck. Load	Normalized Weight						
0°	5	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.998	0.880	0.969	0.340	0.717
	6	-	-	-	-	2.0	1.162	0.570	0.861
	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.880	1.004
30°	5	1.0	1.0	0.919	0.998	0.791	0.969	0.558	0.717
	6	-	-	-	-	1.349	1.162	0.988	0.861
45°	5	1.0	1.0	0.933	0.998	0.756	0.969	0.766	0.717
	6	-	-	-	-	1.311	1.162	1.311	0.861
60°	5	1.0	1.0	0.907	0.908	0.686	0.969	0.919	0.717
	6	-	-	-	-	1.209	1.162	1.500	0.861

Figure 4 Finite Element Discretization for the Square Plate Without a Hole. (Four Sixteen Noded Isoparametric Elements Through the Thickness; $2 \times 2 \times 2$ Gauss Quadrature Scheme for each Element.)

Figure 5 Finite Element Discretization for a Square Plate with a Hole with $d/W = 0.6$. (Four Sixteen Noded Isoparametric Elements through the Thickness.)

Figure 6 Buckling and Post-Buckling Response of the Isotropic Solid Square Plates of Figures 4 Under Displacement and Force Loading.

Figure 7 Buckling and Post-Buckling Response of an Isotropic Square Plate with a Central Circular Hole, $d/w = 0.20$.

Figure 8 Buckling and Post-Buckling Reseponse of an Isotropic Square Plate with a Central Circular Hole, $d/w = 0.40$.

Figure 9 Buckling and Post-Buckling Response of an Isotropic Square Plate with a Central Circular Hole, $d/w = 0.60$. (Force Loading)

Figure 11 Comparison of Post-Buckling Response of Laminated Square Plates with Holes Under Force Loading; $n = 5$, $\theta = 60^\circ$; (i) $d/W = 0.0$, (ii) $d/W = 0.20$.

Figure 12 Comparison of Post-Buckling Response of Laminated Square Plates with Holes Under Force Loading; $n = 5$, $\theta = 60^\circ$; (i) $d/W = 0.0$, (ii) $d/W = 0.50$.

Figure 10 Percent Change in Required Volume for a Given Critical Load of Isotropic Square Plates with Holes.

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